

THE POTENTIAL CONSEQUENCES OF DISREGARDING GRAMMAR AND PUNCTUATION RULES ON SOCIAL MEDIA FOR LANGUAGE LEARNING AND EDUCATION

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Annotation: In today's digital age, social media has become an integral part of our daily lives. Almost everyone uses social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and Telegram for different purposes. However, we can witness that many users usually youngsters don't follow grammar and punctuation rules while writing posts or comments. This article provides potential impacts on communication and language learning and how to solve these problems.

Key words: social media, slang, non-standard English, grammar errors, punctuation, language learning, informal, followers, audiences, abbreviations, communication, consequences, the internet.

These days, social media has become a ubiquitous platform for communication, information sharing, entertainment and social interaction. However, the informal nature of social media has led to a prevalent disregard for grammar and punctuation rules. Most of people use non-standard English and deliberate misspellings while texting messages or posts. This article aims to explore the reasons and impacts of disregarding grammar and punctuation rules on social media and the potential effects it may have on language learning and education.

There are several reasons why most people do not follow grammar rules and punctuation. One of the main reasons is informality. Social media is a casual platform where people communicate quickly and informally. They tend to use shortcuts and abbreviations which may not follow proper grammar rules. Moreover, today's people often write quickly without taking the time to proofread their messages. According to Erika Robinson (2015), "I think this is largely out of laziness. The fact that one is often typing on a phone, writing on the fly and under time constraints makes one pay less attention to the niceties of grammar. Quick communication is the point, rather than correctness or elegance of expression. Also, social media enables everyone to communicate, and while everyone has the capacity and the desire to communicate, not everyone is a grammarian." Another reason is the level of education. Everyone does not have the same level of education, these people who have low level of education may not aware of doing grammar errors. The words you wrote mean who you are. "Proper grammar in your writing is one of the most important elements because it makes a statement about you as a professional and as a person. Also, if you have grammatical errors in your content, you may be hurting your chances of your readers understanding what you are trying to convey" (Carolyn Cohn 17). For example, one day I was watching reels on Instagram, I suddenly encountered one post with some words. The blogger reached 1 million followers but he said that "1m flowers" not 1m followers. I do not know why it was happened, maybe because of speed or poor education. People from different cultures may have different grammar rules, and their use of language may not always align with the standard rules of English.

Today, almost everyone has an access to the internet and many learners use social media for the purpose of resources and practice, but exposure to incorrect grammar and punctuation can lead to the internalization of mistakes. This can occur when individuals are exposed to incorrect grammar, spelling, and punctuation online, and subsequently, adopt these mistakes as part of their own language usage. For instance, many users write "Your welcome" not "You're welcome". Some people who have poor education may think its correct version and they may internalize this word in their writing or speaking.

One of the consequences of consistently neglecting grammar rules on the internet is limited educational and professional. Students who have these issues might encounter challenges in writing assignments, standardized tests, and academic communication. This can lead to lower grades, missed educational opportunities, and potential barriers to higher education. Additionally, in professional environments, poor language skills can affect an individual's ability to convey ideas clearly, write professional documents, and communicate with colleagues and clients.

To avoid grammar errors on social media, we should use some strategies:

1. Proofread before posting:

It is really important to review the post which you want to post on the internet and edit spelling, grammar rules and punctuation or you can use several auto-correction bots or tolls before hitting the button "send".

2. Consider your audience: You should know your audience who are. If you are communicating in a professional context, maintain a higher standard of grammar and punctuation. In more casual settings, you may use some abbreviations, but clarity and correctness are still important.

3. Engage in Language Learning: Continuously improving your language skills can help you avoid grammar errors not only while texting messages but only writing assignments. Consider reading books, articles, and other well-written content to familiarize yourself with proper grammar and punctuation.

CONCLUSION

In summary, in our fast-paced society, it is common to see people who do not pay attention to their words on their posts or comments on social media. Informal communication, laziness and the desire to type quickly are the main causes to make some mistakes while communicating on the internet. It may lead to various impacts like a decline in language proficiency, a lack of understanding of proper writing conventions, and a negative impact on communication skills.

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